

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**NOVEL PENTA- SUBSTITUTED PYRIDINE NUCLEUS WITH
PYRAZOLE ANALOGUES: MICROWAVE ASSISTED
SYNTHESIS, DOCKING AND BIOLOGICAL SCREENING****Rahul P. Thummar*¹, Ronak D. Kamani¹, Nirav H. Sapariya¹, Beena K. Vaghasiya¹, Jemin R. Avalani² and Dipak K. Raval¹**¹Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar- 388 120, Gujarat, India²Shree A. N. Patel P. G. Institute of Science and Research, Anand-388001, Gujarat, India

*Corresponding author. Tel.: +91-02692-226856 - Ext. - 211; Fax: +91-02692 236475.

E-mail: rahulthummar997@gmail.com, dipanalka@yahoo.com**Abstract:**

A novel series of 5-(4-formyl substituted phenoxy)-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbonitrile (**1a-b**) based penta-substituted pyridine derivatives **4(a-n)** was synthesized by piperidine catalyzed cyclocondensation reaction through microwave. The newly synthesized compounds were characterized by spectral studies and also by C, H and N analyses. The synthesized compounds were tested for their in vitro tuberculosis activity against H37Rv strains using rifampicin, isoniazide and ethambutol as the standard drugs. All novel synthesized compounds were tested for their in vitro antimalarial activity against *P. falciparum* strains using quinine and chloroquine as the standard drugs. Molecular docking and pharmacokinetic study were carried out for all the targeted compounds.

Keywords: - antimalarial activity, antituberculosis, docking, microwave assisted, pyridine***Corresponding Author:****Rahul P. Thummar,**

Department of Chemistry,

Sardar Patel University,

Vallabh Vidyanagar- 388 120, Gujarat, India

E-mail: rahulthummar997@gmail.com, dipanalka@yahoo.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press as Rahul P. Thummar *et al.*, Novel Penta- Substituted Pyridine Nucleus with Pyrazole Analogues: Microwave Assisted Synthesis, Docking and Biological Screening, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Malaria, a mosquito-borne disease, is the most critical health evils in the world at the current time [1]. Due to malaria approximate 500 million people get affected per annum and about 3 million deaths happen due to malaria [2-4]. Amongst the four Plasmodium parasites, Plasmodium falciparum is considered responsible for 95% of deaths [5]. The swell of multidrug-resistant Plasmodium falciparum has highlighted the urgent need of discovering new antimalarial drugs.

In the current scenario *tuberculosis* (TB) is a serious global health problem [6]. Approximately 32 % of the overall mankind is infected with TB and every year around 2 million people die and 8 million new people are detected tuberculosis active [7]. The increase of multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) and the emergence of extensively drug-resistant TB (XDR-TB) pose new challenge for the preclusion [8]. Therefore, there is the urgency for the need of novel and effective novel drug to treat TB in a shorter duration with less toxicity and fewer side effects.

Microwave assisted synthesis is a branch of green chemistry that has attained considerable attention in recent years. Chemical transformations involved *via* this technique are eco-friendly, pollution free and offer high yields together with simplicity in processing and handling [9, 10]. The main advantages of microwave-assisted synthesis are rate accelerations, high selectivity, improved yields, less by products, shorter reaction times, and easier work-up [11, 12].

In modern period pyridine derivatives are a very important class of compounds which have good biological activity due to their pharmacological properties. The biologically active cyano pyridine moiety is proving to show potent antifungal [13], antibacterial [14], anticancer [15] and antimicrobial activity [16]. In addition to that substituted 2-amino-3-cyanopyridine derivatives are known for various

biological activities, such as anti-microbial [17], anti-inflammatory [18], potent inhibitor of HIV-1 integrase [19], anti-inflammatory [20] and antimalarial activity [21].

In continuation of our on-going research on various biologically active heterocyclic derivatives [22, 23] and potent biological screening, microwave assisted synthesis of novel 2-amino-6-((4-substituted phenyl)thio)-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy) substituted phenyl)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (**4a-n**) has been contemplated with the view of getting biologically active compounds for pharmaceutical applications.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:**Chemistry**

The starting material 5-(4-formyl substituted phenoxy)-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbonitrile (**1a-b**) was prepared in three step. In the first step Vilsmeier-Haack reaction [24]) of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5(4H)-one gives 5-Chloro-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbaldehyde. In second step 5-Chloro-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbaldehyde containing aldehyde group is converted to nitrile group [25]. The final aldehyde 5-(4-formyl substituted phenoxy)-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbonitrile (**1a-b**) were prepared by nucleophilic displacement of chloro group at C₅ in 5-chloro-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbonitrile (**1a-b**) with substituted 4-hydroxy benzaldehyde by refluxing in DMF using anhydrous K₂CO₃ as a base. The final compounds 2-amino-6-((4-substituted phenyl)thio)-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy) substituted phenyl)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile(**4a-n**) were prepared in good yield (75-90 %) under by microwave irradiation by reacting the mixture of substituted 5-(4-formyl substituted phenoxy)-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbonitrile (**1a-b**), malononitrile (**2**), substituted thiols (**3a-g**) and catalytic amount of piperidine in absolute alcohol for 8-15min at 350 W. (**Table 1**).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 2-amino-6-((4-substituted phenyl)thio)-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy) substituted phenyl)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile derivatives (**4a-n**)

The agreement of target compounds **4(a-n)** may progress via the initial formation of an intermediate afforded by Knoevenagel condensation of a substituted pyrazole aldehyde with malononitrile by loss of water molecule, which would undergo

intermolecular cyclisation of another molecule of malononitrile driven through the nucleophilic attack of thiophenols in presence of piperidine basic reaction medium (**Scheme 2**).

Table 1: Preliminary characterization of synthesized compounds 4a-n.

Entry	R	R ₁	conventional method		Microwave method	
			Time (h)	Yield ^a (%)	Time (min)	Yield ^a (%)
4a	-H	-Cl	1.5	78	09	89
4b	-OCH ₃	-Cl	2	76	10	87
4c	-H	-CH ₃	1.5	81	12	90
4d	-OCH ₃	-CH ₃	2	75	14	88
4e	-H	-Br	1.5	69	12	81
4f	-OCH ₃	-Br	2	68	13	78
4g	-H	-F	1.5	74	09	85
4h	-OCH ₃	-F	2	68	10	81
4i	-H	-OH	1.5	66	11	75
4j	-OCH ₃	-OH	2	60	13	73
4k	-H	-OCH ₃	1.5	63	12	78
4l	-OCH ₃	-OCH ₃	2	64	12	75
4m	-H	-H	1.5	67	14	88
4n	-OCH ₃	-H	2	69	14	83

^aYields of isolated products

Reaction mechanism

Ar = 5-(4-formyl-2-(un) substituted phenoxy)-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbonitrile

Ar' = 4-(un)-substituted thiophenol

Scheme 2. Plausible mechanistic pathway for the synthesis of pyridine derivatives **4(a-n)**

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

¹H NMR, FT-IR, ¹³C NMR, elemental analysis and mass spectrometry techniques were used for confirmation of newly synthesised compounds. The ¹H NMR spectra of compounds **4a-n** showed the presence of $-\text{CH}_3$ protons (pyrazole ring) as a sharp

singlet in the range between δ 2.34-2.45 ppm. The broad singlet at δ 5.45-5.65 ppm was observed due to $-\text{NH}_2$ proton. In the range between δ 7.15-7.78 ppm the signals (multiplets) appeared for aromatic protons. The IR spectrum of compounds **4a-n** exhibited characteristic absorption band in the range

730-771 cm^{-1} which can be ascribed to the presence of thioether linkage. While absorption band in the range of 1212-1231 cm^{-1} was observed for ether linkage. The absorption band in the range 3410-3311 cm^{-1} may be attributed to asymmetric & symmetric stretching of $-\text{NH}_2$. The absorption band was observed in the range of 1369-1376 cm^{-1} may be due to presence of $-\text{CH}_3$ group. The absorption band in the range of 2180-2270 cm^{-1} was observed due to $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching. The mass spectrum of all the compounds showed molecular ion peak (M^+) corresponding to their respective molecular weights, which confirmed the chemical structures.

Table 2: In vitro antituberculosis activity (% inhibition) of compounds (4a-o) against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv (at concentration 250 mg/mL).

Entry	% inhibition	Entry	% inhibition
4a	97	4j	40
4b	95	4k	81
4c	79	4l	72
4d	64	4m	94
4e	57	4n	42
4f	52	Rifampicin	98
4g	98	Ethambutol	99
4h	46	Isoniazide	99
4i	70		

Antituberculosis activity of the all compounds **4a-n** was conducted at 250 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentrations against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv strain. Compounds **4a** (R = 3-H, R_1 = 4-Cl), **4b** (R = 3- CH_3 , R_1 = 4-Cl), **4g** (R = 3-H, R_1 = 4-F) and **4m** (R = 3-H, R_1 = 4-H) were found to have brilliant activity (i.e. **97%**, **95%**, **98%** and **94%** at 250 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv. Remaining all other compounds showed medium inhibition against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv.

Biological result

In vitro antituberculosis activity

Evaluation of all newly synthesized compounds was performed for antituberculosis activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv strain. Screening of all the synthesized compounds was conducted at 250 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ by using Lowenstein-Jensen medium (conventional method) as described by Rattan (22). The observed results are presented in **Table 2** in the form of %inhibition. The standard drugs rifampicin, ethambutol and isoniazid were used for comparison.

In vitro antimalarial activity

In vitro antimalarial activity of the all novel synthesized compounds **7a-n** aligned with *P. falciparum* strain was tested using quinine and chloroquine as the reference drugs. The consequences of the antimalarial screening are communicated as the drug concentration resulting in 50% inhibition (IC_{50}) of parasite growth and are listed in **Table 3**.

Table 3: In vitro antimalarial activity of derivatives 4a-n

Entry	IC_{50} ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Entry	IC_{50} ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
4a	0.023	4i	0.20
4b	0.18	4j	0.59
4c	0.54	4k	0.042
4d	1.84	4l	0.98
4e	0.37	4m	1.58
4f	0.75	4n	1.65
4g	0.057	Quinine	0.268
4h	1.61	Chloroquine	0.020

The compounds **4a** (R = -H, R₁ = 2,4-di Cl), **4g** (R = -H, R₁ = 2-CH₃), **4k** (R = -H, R₁ = 2-OCH₃), were found to have IC₅₀ 0.023, 0.057 and 0.042 respectively. In this antimalarial screening only three compounds were found to be more active against *P. falciparum*.

5. Docking study of compounds

In silico pharmacokinetic evaluation

The different pharmacokinetic parameters viz. hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA), hydrogen bond donor (HBD), rotatable bonds (Rot B), logP, polar surface area (PSA) and binding energy *s* for compounds **4a-n** are listed in **Table-4**. These data were evaluated by molecule docking server software. The synthesized compounds have a high molecular weight (≤ 500) as compared to the standard drugs. The compounds **4j** and **4l** showed elevated hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA) value while **4i** and **4j** have a high hydrogen bond donor value. The values of rotational bond of all synthesized compounds (**4a-n**) are in between **6-9** which is very near to ethambutol. All compounds showed higher than logP (≤ 5) values and polar surface area then isoniazide and ethambutol.

In silico molecular docking study

Molecular interaction for all the ligands was studied using molecule docking server software. The 3D diagrams **Figs 1A-4A** show the binding sites of all the ligands within the receptor (2B35). **Figs. 1B-4B** show 2D interaction diagram between amino acids and compounds that interacted to the active sites (amino acids) of receptor (2B35) through like a hydrogen bond. We performed molecular docking studies of all compounds (**4a-n**) and 3D presentation of the complex between receptor (PDB ID: 2B35). Ethambutol and isoniazide were used as the standard drugs. The binding energy docking scores are presented in **Table-3**. It is remarkable that all the compounds (**4a-n**) showed binding energy in between **-6.39** to **-8.26** kcal/mol and formed stronger complexes with receptor as compared to the standard drugs. Compounds **4a**, **4b**, **4g** and **4m** showed very poor binding energy (**-8.22**, **-8.26**, **-8.02**, and **-8.03** kcal/mol. respectively) which are potently active against tuberculosis (**Table-2**).

Table 4: Pharmacokinetic parameters

Compound ID(s)	Mol.wt ^a	HBA ^b	HBD ^c	RotB ^d	logp ^e	PSA ^f	Binding energy ^g
4a	560.02	8	1	6	7.61	162.63	-8.22
4b	590.05	9	1	7	7.62	171.86	-8.26
4c	539.61	8	1	6	7.27	162.63	-7.68
4d	569.63	9	1	7	7.28	171.86	-6.55
4e	604.48	8	1	6	7.72	162.63	-7.32
4f	634.50	9	1	7	7.73	171.86	-7.79
4g	543.57	8	1	6	7.10	162.63	-8.02
4h	573.60	9	1	7	7.11	171.86	-7.12
4i	541.58	9	2	6	6.67	182.86	-7.58
4j	571.60	10	2	7	6.67	192.09	-6.39
4k	555.61	9	1	7	6.97	171.86	-6.83
4l	585.63	10	1	8	6.98	181.09	-6.78
4m	525.58	8	1	6	6.96	162.63	-8.03
4n	555.61	9	1	7	6.91	171.86	-7.63
Isoniazide	137.13	4	2	2	0.77	68.01	-5.1
Ethambutol	204.30	4	4	9	0.48	64.52	-4.5

^a Molecular Weight ≤ 500 (gm/mol) [26], ^b Hydrogen Bond Acceptor ≤ 10 [27], ^c Hydrogen Bond Donor ≤ 5 [27], ^d Rotatable Bonds ≤ 10 [27], ^e logP ≤ 5 [26], ^f Polar Surface Area ≤ 140 Å² [27], ^g Binding energy

Experimental section

Starting materials were obtained from Spectrochem and Sigma Aldrich. The progress of the reactions was checked by TLC on aluminum plates coated with silica gel 60 F254, 0.25 mm thickness (Merck). The developed chromatograms were visualized under UV light. FT-IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum GX FT-IR Spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer, USA). The ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance 400. Tetramethylsilane (TMS) was used as the internal standard and CDCl_3 as the

solvent. Chemical shifts are reported in parts per million (ppm). Melting points are uncorrected and were determined using $\mu\text{ThermoCal10}$ melting point apparatus (Analab Scientific Pvt. Ltd, India). The elemental analysis was performed on Perkin-Elmer 2400 series-II elemental analyzer (Perkin-Elmer, USA) at (SICART), Vallabh Vidyanagar, India. Mass spectra were recorded on Shimadzu LCMS 2010 spectrometer (Shimadzu, Tokyo, Japan) at Sardar Patel University (PURSE programme of DST), Vallabh Vidyanagar.

Fig.1 (A) 3D presentation of the complex between receptor (**2B35**) and **4a**.
(B) Schematic 2D diagram of interaction between active site residues and **4a**.

Fig.2 (A) 3D presentation of the complex between receptor (**2B35**) and **4b**.
(B) Schematic 2D diagram of interaction between active site residues and **4b**.

1214 (C-O-C str.), 730 (C-S-C str.), 3018 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.37 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 3.93 (s, 3H, -OCH₃) 5.65 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.17-7.75 (m, 13H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 13.43, 56.41, 78.83, 87.53, 95.65, 111.45, 113.49, 114.53, 114.84, 121.60, 121.99, 123.03, 125.43, 128.05, 129.25, 129.65, 132.31, 136.56, 136.99, 137.11, 144.49, 151.23, 151.55, 153.60, 156.91, 159.28, 168.67, LC-MS: 590.06 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. For C₃₁H₂₀ClN₇O₂S; Elemental Analysis: C, 63.10; H, 3.42; N, 16.62; Observed, C, 62.80; H, 3.23; N, 16.14 %.

2-amino-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)phenyl)-6-(p-tolylthio)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4c)

White solid; yield: 84; mp 165-167 °C IR (KBr, ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) = 3419 & 3315 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2180 (-C≡N stretching), 1369 (-CH₃ str.), 1226 (C-O-C str.), 769 (C-S-C str.), 3015 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.35 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 2.36 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 5.45 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.18-7.56 (m, 13H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 13.55, 21.45, 81.63, 87.04, 95.47, 111.46, 114.71, 114.98, 115.04, 118.28, 122.92, 123.40, 128.50, 129.47, 130.20, 130.46, 130.95, 135.67, 136.59, 140.39, 151.80, 152.07, 156.59, 159.32, 169.73; LC-MS: 539.62 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. For C₃₁H₂₁N₇O₂S; Elemental Analysis: C, 69.00; H, 3.92; N, 18.17; Observed, C, 68.67; H, 3.85; N, 17.97 %.

2-amino-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)-3-methoxy-phenyl)-6-(p-tolylthio)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4d)

White solid; yield: 83; mp 156-160 °C IR (KBr, ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) = 3445 & 3335 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2194 (-C≡N stretching), 1375 (-CH₃ str.), 1219 (C-O-C str.), 752 (C-S-C str.), 3012 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.34 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.36 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 3.91 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 5.48 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.17-7.74 (m, 13H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 13.58, 21.47, 56.45, 82.03, 86.59, 97.14, 112.40, 113.91, 114.90, 115.14, 119.08, 122.45, 123.85, 127.10, 129.49, 130.27, 131.01, 132.25, 134.43, 135.50, 140.19, 140.397, 143.81, 151.40, 152.47, 157.54, 160.02, 168.99; LC-MS: 569.64 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. For C₃₂H₂₃N₇O₂S; Elemental Analysis: C, 67.47; H, 4.07; N, 17.21; Observed, C, 67.30; H, 3.88; N, 17.04 %.

2-amino-6-((4-bromophenyl)thio)-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)-phenyl)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4e)

White solid; yield: 89; mp 190-194 °C IR (KBr, ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) = 3418 & 3333 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2295 (-C≡N stretching), 1372 (-CH₃ str.), 1220 (C-O-C str.), 742 (C-S-C str.), 2990 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.35 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 5.46 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.19-7.78 (m,

13H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 12.96, 76.70, 85.10, 95.59, 111.15, 114.41, 115.04, 120.10, 121.6, 125.15, 126.50, 129.11, 130.05, 131.45, 132.24, 137.58, 139.15, 140.52, 146.15, 15.03, 152.64, 157.55, 159.54, 169.02; LC-MS: 604.49 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. For C₃₀H₁₈BrN₇O₂S; Elemental Analysis: C, 59.61; H, 3.00; N, 16.22; Observed, C, 59.29; H, 2.88; N, 15.98 %.

2-amino-6-((4-bromophenyl)thio)-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)-3-methoxyphenyl)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4f)

White solid; yield: 79; mp 169-173 °C IR (KBr, ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) = 3442 & 3351 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2215 (-C≡N stretching), 1374 (-CH₃ str.), 1222 (C-O-C str.), 764 (C-S-C str.), 3005 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.39 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 3.94 (s, 3H, -OCH₃) 5.67 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.15-7.72 (m, 13H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 13.43, 56.41, 78.82, 87.54, 95.63, 111.45, 113.50, 114.52, 114.83, 121.59, 121.98, 123.03, 124.84, 126.09, 128.05, 129.25, 132.31, 132.60, 136.99, 137.30, 144.49, 151.23, 151.55, 153.61, 156.9, 159.30, 168.48; LC-MS: 634.51 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. For C₃₁H₂₀BrN₇O₂S; Elemental Analysis: C, 58.68; H, 3.18; N, 15.45; Observed, C, 58.54; H, 2.97; N, 15.19 %.

2-amino-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)phenyl)-6-((4-fluoro-phenyl)thio)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4g)

White solid; yield: 85; mp 192-195 °C IR (KBr, ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) = 3458 & 3342 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2211 (-C≡N stretching), 1375 (-CH₃ str.), 1213 (C-O-C str.), 738 (C-S-C str.), 3011 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.45 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 5.55 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.17-7.62 (m, 13H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 13.56, 81.63, 87.04, 95.47, 111.46, 114.71, 115.04, 118.28, 122.92, 123.40, 128.50, 129.29, 129.47, 129.63, 133.33, 136.91, 139.11, 147.49, 151.28, 151.55, 153.60, 156.91, 160.28, 167.47; LC-MS: 543.58 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. For C₃₀H₁₈FN₇O₂S; Elemental Analysis: C, 66.29; H, 3.34; N, 18.04; Observed, C, 66.01; H, 3.21; N, 17.85 %.

2-amino-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)-3-methoxy-phenyl)-6-((4-fluorophenyl)thio)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4h)

White solid; yield: 84; mp 210-213 °C IR (KBr, ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) = 3420 & 3347 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2208 (-C≡N stretching), 1376 (-CH₃ str.), 1215 (C-O-C str.), 752 (C-S-C str.), 2979 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.34 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 3.90 (s, 3H, -OCH₃) 5.60 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.19-7.77 (m, 13H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 14.03, 57.01, 78.93, 89.25, 98.05, 112.41, 113.99, 114.03, 115.74, 120.28, 121.09,

123.03, 124.83, 127.45, 129.25, 131.45, 132.81, 135.91, 136.54, 137.82, 143.67, 151.57, 152.51, 154.29, 156.82, 160.21, 168.60; LC-MS: 534.64 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. For C₃₁H₂₀FN₇O₂S; Elemental Analysis: C, 64.91; H, 3.51; N, 17.09; Observed, C, 64.79; H, 3.47; N, 16.86 %.

2-amino-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)phenyl)-6-((4-hydroxyphenyl)thio)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4i)

White solid; yield: 81; mp 209-211 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹) = 3438 & 3311 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2299 (-C≡N stretching), 1372 (-CH₃ str.), 1223 (C-O-C str.), 771 (C-S-C str.), 3019 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.40 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 5.66 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.16-7.72 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 9.24 (s, 1H, -OH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 14.04, 82.61, 87.14, 94.97, 112.41, 114.76, 115.54, 119.59, 122.49, 125.41, 129.80, 129.99, 130.05, 130.48, 132.30, 137.51, 139.11, 148.19, 151.28, 152.05, 153.40, 157.51, 161.18, 167.59; LC-MS: 541.59 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc.: C₃₀H₁₉N₇O₂S For; Elemental Analysis: C, 66.53; H, 3.54; N, 18.10; Observed, C, 66.45; H, 3.19; N, 17.94 %.

2-amino-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)-3-methoxyphenyl)-6-((4-hydroxyphenyl)thio)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4j)

White solid; yield: 90 mp 222-225 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹) = 3452 & 3337 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2208 (-C≡N stretching), 1371 (-CH₃ str.), 1224 (C-O-C str.), 765 (C-S-C str.), 2983 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.38 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 3.92 (s, 3H, -OCH₃) 5.64 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.18-7.73 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 9.25 (s, 1H, -OH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 14.07, 56.49, 78.88, 87.40, 95.40, 112.45, 113.94, 114.54, 115.58, 120.19, 121.49, 123.53, 126.17, 129.13, 129.95, 130.48, 131.58, 135.43, 136.90, 137.01, 140.19, 152.53, 153.50, 153.80, 156.82, 159.58, 168.98; LC-MS: 571.62 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. C₃₁H₂₁N₇O₃S : For; Elemental Analysis: C, 65.14; H, 3.70; N, 17.15; Observed, C, 64.99; H, 4.06; N, 17.01 %.

2-amino-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)phenyl)-6-((4-methoxyphenyl)thio)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4k)

White solid; yield: 83; mp 218-221 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹) = 3421 & 3330 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2270 (-C≡N stretching), 1375 (-CH₃ str.), 1220 (C-O-C str.), 747 (C-S-C str.), 3005 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.35 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 3.91 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 5.59 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.20-7.72 (m, 13H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 13.58, 21.46, 81.59, 88.05, 96.92, 112.40, 113.54, 114.90, 115.54, 117.24, 121.42, 123.40, 128.80, 129.07, 130.46, 130.46,

131.64, 134.15, 136.9, 144.51, 152.59, 158.07, 155.49, 160.12, 169.75; LC-MS: 555.62 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. C₃₁H₂₁N₇O₂S: For; Elemental Analysis: C, 67.01; H, 3.81; N, 17.65; Observed, C, 66.91; H, 3.57; N, 17.43 %.

2-amino-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)-3-methoxyphenyl)-6-((4-methoxyphenyl)thio)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4l)

White solid; yield: 79; mp 220-223 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹) = 3410 & 3312 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2189 (-C≡N stretching), 1370 (-CH₃ str.), 1222 (C-O-C str.), 721 (C-S-C str.), 2999 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.34 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 3.88 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 3.93 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 5.57 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.19-7.70 (m, 13H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 14.05, 22.14, 57.25, 83.17, 86.50, 97.84, 111.10, 113.91, 114.95, 114.54, 118.88, 122.49, 125.05, 128.84, 129.79, 130.47, 131.91, 132.05, 133.43, 138.00, 141.51, 142.97, 143.01, 151.40, 153.94, 159.04, 160.09, 167.48; LC-MS: 585.64 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. C₃₂H₂₃N₇O₃S: For Elemental Analysis: C, 65.63; H, 3.96; N, 16.74; Observed, C, 65.48; H, 3.76; N, 16.57 %.

2-amino-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)phenyl)-6-(phenylthio)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4m)

White solid; yield: 80; mp 219-222 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹) = 3441 & 3324 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2212 (-C≡N stretching), 1375 (-CH₃ str.), 1212 (C-O-C str.), 749 (C-S-C str.), 3007 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.37 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 5.58 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.17-7.71 (m, 9H, -Ar-H), ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 13.60, 81.85, 87.15, 99.69, 112.58, 113.91, 116.81, 119.18, 122.92, 124.50, 129.45, 129.99, 130.47, 130.69, 132.13, 138.51, 139.01, 149.45, 150.27, 151.55, 154.40, 157.61, 162.08, 168.57; LC-MS: 525.59 (M)⁺; Anal.Calc. C₃₀H₁₉N₇O₂S: For; Elemental Analysis: C, 68.56; H, 3.64; N, 18.66; Observed, C, 65.48; H, 3.47; N, 18.48 %.

2-amino-4-(4-((4-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)oxy)-3-methoxyphenyl)-6-(phenylthio)pyridine-3,5-dicarbonitrile (4n)

White solid; yield: 90; mp 227-230 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹) = 3430 & 3320 (asym. & sym. stretching of -NH₂); 2182 (C≡N stretching), 1374 (-CH₃ str.), 1219 (C-O-C str.), 751 (C-S-C str.), 2987 (Ar-C-H); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ = 2.35 (s, 3H, Pyrazole -CH₃), 3.90 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 5.61 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 7.15-7.73 (m, 13H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 13.45, 56.42, 78.83, 87.26, 95.52, 111.46, 113.52, 114.71, 114.97, 121.61, 121.95, 123.03, 127.02, 125.06, 129.26, 129.39, 130.02, 132.46, 135.79, 136.98, 144.41, 151.19, 151.55,

153.63, 156.83, 159.31, 169.26; LC-MS: 555.62 (M)+; Anal.Calc. C₃₁H₂₁N₇O₂S: For; Elemental Analysis: C, 67.01; H, 3.81; N, 17.65; Observed, C, 66.66; H, 3.64; N, 17.48 %.

CONCLUSION:

A highly sustainable and efficient multicomponent synthesis of novel penta- substituted pyridine bearing a pyrazole scaffolds under microwave irradiation is reported. The notable features of this methodology are eco-friendly reaction conditions, no side product, the avoidance of toxic catalysts and easy purification. Amongst the all novel tested compounds **4a**, **4g** and **4k** showed more potent antimalarial activities against *P. falciparum* Compounds **4a**, **4b**, **4g** and **4m** have shown brilliant anti tuberculosis activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv strains as well as very poor binding energy in molecule docking study as compared to isoniazide and ethambutol. Compounds 4a and 4g are more potent against both activity *viz.* antimalarial and antituberculosis.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS:

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University for providing necessary research facilities. RPT acknowledges University Grants Commission-New Delhi, India for Basic Scientific Research (UGC-BSR) Fellowship awarded to him during 2015–2017. The authors are also thankful to NFDD centre of excellent, Saurashtra University, Rajkot for ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy. The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Pharmaceutical Science, Sardar Patel University for providing FT-IR facility. We are also thankful to the DST-Purse, Vallabh Vidyanagar for providing mass analysis and Dhanji P. Rajani, Microcare Laboratory, Surat, for biological screening of the compounds reported herein.

REFERENCES:

- 1.Kumar A., Paliwal D., Saini D., Thakur A. Aggarwal, S., Kaushik D., A comprehensive review on synthetic approach for antimalarial agents, European journal of medicinal chemistry, 2014; 85: 147-178.
- 2.Küçükgülmez Ş.G., Şenkardeş S., Recent advances in bioactive pyrazoles, European journal of medicinal chemistry, 2015; 97: 786-815.
- 3.R.D. Newman, World malaria report 2011, (2012).
- 4.Rosenthal P.J., 2001. Antimalarial chemotherapy: mechanisms of action, resistance, and new directions in drug discovery, Springer Science & Business Media,
- 5.Sapariya N.H., Vaghasiya B.K., Thummar R.P., Kamani R.D., Patel K.H., Thakor P., Thakkar S.S., Ray A., Raval D.K., Synthesis, characterization, in

silico molecular docking study and biological evaluation of a 5-(phenylthio) pyrazole based polyhydroquinoline core moiety, New Journal of Chemistry, 2017; 41: 10686-10694.

6.W.H. Organization, Global tuberculosis report 2016.

7.Dye C., Global epidemiology of tuberculosis, 2006. The Lancet, 367; 938-940.

8.Harikrishna N., Isloor A. M, Ananda K., Parish T., Jamalis J., Ghabbour H. A, Fun H.-K., Antitubercular and Antimicrobial Activity of NH₄VO₃ Promoted 1, 4-Dihydropyridine Incorporated 1, 3, 4-trisubstituted Pyrazole, Letters in Drug Design & Discovery, 2017; 14: 699-711.

9.Akhtar W., Khan M.F., Verma G., Shaquiquzzaman M., Akhter M., Marella A., Parmar S., Khatoun R., Alam M.M., Coumarin-Pyrazoline Derivatives: Their One-Pot Microwave Assisted Synthesis and Antimalarial Activity, Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medicinal Chemistry, 2017;3.

10.Shah J., Mohanraj K., Comparison of conventional and microwave-assisted synthesis of benzotriazole derivatives, Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences, 2014;76: 46.

11.Mahmoodi N.O., Mohammadgholipour S., Ghanbari Pirbasti F., Microwave-assisted one-pot three-component synthesis of thiazolidinones using KSF@ Ni as an efficient heterogeneous catalyst, Journal of Sulfur Chemistry, 2017: 1-11.

12.Rostom S.A., Bekhit A.A., Microwave-assisted synthesis of certain pyrrolylpyridines, some derived ring systems and their evaluation as anticancer and antioxidant agents, European journal of medicinal chemistry, 2015; 92: 712-722.

13.Liu X.H., Sun Z.H., Yang M.Y., Tan C.X., Weng J.Q., Zhang Y.G., Y. Ma, Microwave Assisted One Pot Synthesis, Crystal Structure, Antifungal Activities and 3D-QSAR of Novel 1, 2, 4-Triazolo [4, 3-a] pyridines, Chemical biology & drug design, 2014; 84: 342-347.

14.Dandia A., Sehgal V., Singh P, Synthesis of fluorine containing 2-aryl-3-pyrazolyl/pyranyl/isoxazolonyl-indole derivatives as antifungal and antibacterial agents, Indian journal of chemistry. Sect. B: Organic chemistry, including medical chemistry, 1993;32:1288-1291.

15.Sangani C.B., Makawana, Zhang .A.X., Teraiya S.B., Lin L., Zhu H.-L., Design, synthesis and molecular modeling of pyrazole–quinoline–pyridine hybrids as a new class of antimicrobial and anticancer agents, European journal of medicinal chemistry, 2014;76: 549-557.

16.Gad-Elkareem M.A., Abdel-Fattah A.M., Elneairy M.A., Pyridine-2 (1 H)-thione in heterocyclic synthesis: synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some new thio-substituted ethyl nicotinate, thieno [2,

3-b] pyridine and pyridothienopyrimidine derivatives, *Journal of Sulfur Chemistry*, 2011; 32: 273-286.

17.Vyas D., Tala S., Akbari J., Dhaduk M., Joshi K., Joshi H., Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some new cyanopyridine and cyanopyrans towards *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and other microorganisms, 2009; 48B:833-839

18.Murata T., Shimada M. a, Sakakibara S., Yoshino T., Kadono H., Masuda T., Shimazaki M., Shintani T., Fuchikami K., Sakai K., Discovery of novel and selective IKK- β serine-threonine protein kinase inhibitors. Part 1, *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry letters*, 2003;13: 913-918.

19.Deng J., Sanchez T., Al-Mawsawi L.Q., Dayam R., Yunes R.A., Garofalo A., Bolger M.B., Neamati N., Discovery of structurally diverse HIV-1 integrase inhibitors based on a chalcone pharmacophore, *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry*, 2007;15: 4985-5002.

20.Filosa R., Peduto A., Di Micco S., Caprariis P. de, Festa M., Petrella A. Capranico G., Bifulco G., R=(a) C₆H₅ (b) C₂H₅ (c) C₆H₁₃, *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 2009;17: 1-12.

21.Kruggel S., Lemcke T., Meijer L., Kunick C., Wiebke Fugel, Anselm Erich Oberholzer, Bernhard Gschloessl, Ron Dzikowski, Narkiss Pressburger, Lutz Preu, Laurence H. Pearl, L Blandine Baratte, Morgane Ratin, Ilya Okun, Christian Doerig, 2012.

22.Kalaria P.N., Satasia S.P., Avalani J.R., Raval D.K., Ultrasound-assisted one-pot four-component synthesis of novel 2-amino-3-cyanopyridine derivatives bearing 5-imidazopyrazole scaffold and

their biological broadcast, *European journal of medicinal chemistry*, 2014;83: 655-664.

23.Thummar R.P., Kamani R.D., Sapariya N.H., Vaghasiya B.K., Karad S.C., Raval D.K., Synthesis And Biological Evaluation Of Certain Pyrazole Clubbed 1, 3-Thiazolone Derivatives Bearing Pyrazoline Moiety, *Heterocyclic Letters*, 2017; 7: 347-356.

24.Horrocks P., Pickard M., Parekh H., Patel S., Pathak R.B., Synthesis and biological evaluation of 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-substituted pyrazole derivatives, *Organic & biomolecular chemistry*, 2013; 11: 4891-4898.

25.Karad S.C., Purohit V.B., Thummar R.P., Vaghasiya B.K., Kamani R.D., Thakor P., Thakkar V.R., Thakkar S.S., Ray A., Raval D.K., Synthesis and biological screening of novel 2-morpholinoquinoline nucleus clubbed with 1, 2, 4-oxadiazole motifs, *European journal of medicinal chemistry*, 2017;126: 894-909.

26.Sondhi S.M., Johar M., Rajvanshi S., Dastidar S.G., Shukla R., Raghbir R., Lown J.W., Anticancer, anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity evaluation of heterocyclic compounds synthesized by the reaction of 4-isothiocyanato-4-methylpentan-2-one with substituted o-phenylenediamines, o-diaminopyridine and (un) substituted o, *Australian Journal of Chemistry*, 2001; 54: 69-74.

27.Gangjee A., Vidwans A., Elzein E., McGuire J.J., Queener S.F., Kisliuk R.L., Synthesis, antifolate, and antitumor activities of classical and nonclassical 2-amino-4-oxo-5-substituted-pyrrolo [2, 3-d] pyrimidines, *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 2001;44: 1993-2003.